

Data Access Application Programming Interface

MSI contributed with the development of a data interface to provide Cognitive Production plants in the process industry a solution to the challenge to obtain validated and representative data in a standard way. A standard API interface definition which allows to access in a simple way to the heterogenous data structures obtained from the multiple process data sources. So, it will be in charge to get data form a highly heterogeneous set of sources and transform them into generic and configurable industrial data spaces for the process industry to be used for e.g. Digital twin development. It covers three type of data structures being (i) Real Time data defined as *Signals*, (ii) historical time series defined as *Measurements* and (iii) structured data structures defined as *Records* (SQL).

To facilitate access to data and accelerate Cognitive Sensors and Digital Twin integrations two services have been created for each data type: one to know the parameters included on the available datasets and another one to access the values of these parameters.

Authorization

All the following methods are secured against different types of cyberattacks and unauthorized access so, to make use of them, the data consumer must know the endpoint URL and must have a valid access token. All API calls must contain in the header an access-token with the value of the TOKEN that identifies the receiver as an authorized user.

1. Signals (Real Time data)

Signals are the process parameters. They are defined in the database as master data.

By accessing **https:// [ENDPOINT URL] / api / signals (GET)** the consumer will be able to know which signals has access to and with what permission (R-Read, W-Write or RW-Read write). This call will return a list in JSON format, in which each element will correspond to the definition of a signal.

Example structure:

```
[
  {
    "name": "Descriptive name of the signal",
    "field": "Technical name of the signal",
    "unit": "Physical unit of measurement",
    "access": "R-Read, W-Write or RW-Read write",
    "type": "Data type: String, Integer, Decimal, Boolean, ..."
  }
]
```

By accessing **https:// [Endpoint URL] / api / signals-get (POST)** the consumer will be able to access to a value of one signal. The call to the method must be done sending the technical name of the signal from which the consumer wants to obtain its value in a JSON format at the body of the call.

Example structure:

```
[
  "Technical name of the signal"
]
```

Example structure:

```
[
  "Actual value of the signal"
]
```

2. Measurements (Time Series Data)

Measurement is understood as a group of signals, which contains values of each of the signal over time.

In addition to being able to access raw historical data, the system allows access to preprocessed data using different aggregation functions over time periods such as:

- Mean
- Maximum
- Minimum
- Sum
- Standard deviation
- ...

To access to the historical raw or aggregated values, the consumer will have to know to which measurements they belong.

By accessing **https:// [ENDPOINT URL] / api / measurement (GET)** the consumer will be able to know which measurements, and which signals has access to and with what permission. This call will return a list in JSON format, in which each element at top level will correspond to the definition of a measurement, and below each measurement the signals that are included in it.

Example structure:

```
[
  {
    "name": " Name of the measurement ",
    "description": "Description of the measurement",
    "access": "R-Read, W-Write or RW-Read write",
    "fields": [
      {
```

```

        "name": "Descriptive name of the signal",
        "field": "Technical name of the signal",
        "unit": "Physical unit of measurement",
        "type": "Data type: String, Integer, Decimal, Boolean,
... "
    }
  ]
}
]

```

Obtaining historical values of the signals is done by requesting the measurement that contains the desired signal and by indicating some parameters as defined hereunder.

Accessing **https:// [ENDPOINT URL] / api / measurements-get (POST)** the consumer will have to provide in the body an object (in JSON format) with the following options that will apply to the requested dataset:

- Aggregate function
- Conditions
- Grouping for aggregate function
- Order
- Limit
- Offset

Example structure:

```

{
  "measurement": "Name of the requested measurement to obtain data from",
  // Name of the fields of those measurements to obtain data from
  "fields": [
    {
      "field": "Technical name of the signal",
      "function": "Data aggregation function to be applied",
      // The following aggregation functions can be applied: COUNT (), DISTINCT (), MEAN (), SUM (), FIRST (), LAST (), MAX (), MIN ()
      "as": "New name (ALIAS) of the field after applying the aggregate function"
    }
  ],
  // Filters to apply on the select of the data
  "where": {
    // Limit result by dates
    "condition": "AND",
    "fields": [
      // Measurements after a date (greater than)
      {
        "condition": ">",
        "fields": [

```

```

        "time",
        "'2020-03-13T19:00:00Z'"
    ]
},
// Measurements before a date (less than)
{
    "condition": "<",
    "fields": [
        "time",
        "'2020-03-13T21:00:00Z'"
    ]
}
]
},
// Data aggregation by time: d (Days), h (Hours), m (Minutes) or s
(Seconds)
"groupBy": "time(10m)",
// Signals values sorted descending (DESC) or ascending (ASC)
"order": "DESC",
// Limit the number of results
"limit": 10,
// Offset to define from which record to start obtaining the results.
This is very useful for paging systems
"offset": 0
}

```

This call will return a list in JSON format, in which each element will correspond to the value of the signals in an instant of time.

Example structure:

```

[
  {
    "time": "Time stamp of the measurement",
    "field": "Value of signal 1 (or Alias)",
    "field": "Value of signal 2 (or Alias)",
    // ...
  },
  {
    // ...
  }
]

```

3. Records (SQL Data)

A record is a line in a table in the SQL database.

By accessing **https:// [ENDPOINT URL] / api / records (GET)** the consumer will be able to know which tables, and which fields has access to and with what permission. This call will return a list in JSON format, in which each element will correspond to the definition of a table. For each table the consumer will be able to obtain the fields it contains.

Example structure:

```
[
  {
    "name": "Name of table",
    "description": "Description of table",
    "access": "Access type: R-Read, W-Write or RW-Read write",
    "fields": [
      {
        "name": "Name of field",
        "description": "Description of field",
        "type": "Data type: String, Integer, Decimal, Boolean,
... ",
        "required": true, // Indicate if it is a required field
        "key": true // Indicate if it is a key field
      },
      {
        //...
      }
    ]
  }
]
```

As with historical time series data, SQL data can be requested from the service in an aggregated form using different functions.

Accessing **https:// [ENDPOINT URL] / api / records-get (POST)** the consumer will have to provide in the body an object (in JSON format) with the following options that will apply to the requested dataset:

- Aggregate function
- Conditions
- Grouping for aggregate function
- Order
- Limit
- Offset

Example structure:

```
{
  "table": "Name of the table to obtain data from",
  // Name of the fields of that table to obtain the values from
  "fields": [
    {
      "name": "Name of field",
```

```

        // The following aggregation functions can be applied:
COUNT(), MAX(), MIN(), SUM(), AVG(), ...
        "function": "Function to be applied to get only one value
from the group",
        "as": "New name (ALIAS) of the field after applying the
aggregate function"
    },
    {
        //...
    }
],
// Filters to apply on the select of the data
"where": {
    // Condition that will apply between the fields that are given
below. The following conditions can be applied: AND, OR, =, !=, <, <=, >,
>=, LIKE
    "condition": "AND",
    // Fields for the condition
    "fields": [
        {
            "condition": ">",
            "fields": [
                "CAMP_1",
                1
            ]
        },
        {
            "condition": "LIKE",
            "fields": [
                "CAMP_2",
                "%A%"
            ]
        }
    ]
},
// Data aggregation by one or more fields
"groupBy": [
    "CAMP_1",
    "CAMP_2"
],
// Result sorted by one or more fields
"order": [
    {
        // Sort field
        "field": "CAMP_2",
        // Field values sorted descending (DESC) or ascending (ASC)
        "direction": "DESC"
    }
],

```

```
// Limit the number of results
"limit": 5,
// Offset to define from which record to start obtaining the results.
This is very useful for paging systems
"offset": 0
}
```

This call will return a list in JSON format, in which each element will correspond to the values of fields in one record.

Example structure:

```
[
  {
    "field": "Value of field 1 (or Alias)",
    "field": "Value of field 2 (or Alias)"
    //...
  },
  {
    //...
  }
]
```